

Land-cover types and distribution of bird species at Sabei and Kyesin copper mine area, Monywa District

Khin Ma Ma*

Abstract

Eleven land-cover types could be classified in and around the copper mine project area; creek, tailing pond, waste dump, mine pit area, secondary forest, human habitation, revegetation, shrub land, marsh grassland (wet land), leach pad and agriculture land. A total of 66 bird species of 38 families were recorded at the copper mine project area during the study period. Basically, two kinds of birds, terrestrial and aquatic bird species were recorded. Among the record species, Burmese Collared-dove *Streptopelia xanthocyclus*, Ayarwaddy bulbul *Pycnonotus blanfordi*, Burmese bush lark *Mirafra microptera*, Burmese prinia *Prinia cooki*, Hooded treepie *Crypsirina cucullata* and White throated babbler *Turdoides gularis* were recorded as endemic species at the study area. Oriental darter *Anhinga melanogaster* and River Lapwing *Vanellus duvaucelii* were observed as near threaten species. The highest number of bird species was recorded in Yamar upstream, while the lowest number occurred in marsh grassland (wetland) area. Species diversity index value was highest ($H'=1.49$) in Yamar upstream area and followed by those of the Yamar downstream area ($H'=1.36$) and Khamauktaung area ($H'=1.31$).

Keywords: diversity, endemic, migratory, habitat

Introduction

The study focuses on land-cover types and distribution of bird species at Sabei and Kyesin copper mine area. Birds respond any environmental change with either positively or negatively. Birds also occupy at the top of the food chain in various types of habitats. As top predators, birds play an important part in recycling energy and maintaining ecological balance in the ecosystems. Study of birds can tell about the habitats, and the loss of birds from a specific habitat is a measure of a more general deterioration in biodiversity and environment. Places those are rich in bird species are rich in other forms of biodiversity, thus birds can be used as parameters of ecosystem health. Consequently they are good environmental indicators, and can be used to examine the environmental changes and quality of particular habitat. Many bird species also play a vital role in the control of agricultural pests (Smythies, 2001).

The present study was conducted at the Copper mine project area of Myanmar YanTse Copper Company Limited (MYTCL), situated in Salingyi Township, Monywa District in Sagaing Region. Copper exploration was conducted in the area since 1930s by British, Japanese and Yugoslavian groups in conjunction with the Ministry of Mine, Myanmar. Myanmar Ivanhoe Copper Company Limited (MICCL) has first produced copper in 1998 at a rate of over 27,000 tonnes per year (Muir, 1998). Myanmar YanTse Copper Company Limited is now operating the copper exploration in Sabei and Kyesin areas.

Different habitat types including hilly forest area, revegetation area and water bodies exist at Sabei and Kyesin copper mine project area. Bird species diversity values can be varied among the habitat types. Furthermore, bird species which inhabit in Sabei and Kyesin areas may be important components of biodiversity in the area.

Thus the present research is intended to conduct with the following objectives;

- to classify the land-cover types of Sabei and Kyesin copper mine area using Geographic Information System (GIS)
- to investigate the occurrence of bird species in the Sabei and Kyesin Copper mine area
- to examine the diversity of bird species in the copper mine area

* Dr., Associate Professor, Department of Zoology, Bago University

Materials and methods

Study area

The Copper mine project area is located in Salingyi Township, Monywa District in Sagaing Region, approximately 10 km due west of the town of Monywa at 22° 7' N latitude and 95° 2' E longitude (Fig. 2).

Study period

The study was conducted from June to October 2019.

Data collection

Land-cover and topographic features of the copper Mine project area were studied using Geographic Information System (GIS) and Remote Sensing (RS).

Birds were observed with binoculars and identified using field guides. Point count and opportunistic methods were used in data collection (Bibby et.al., 1992, 1998). Birds were identified according to Smithies (1953, 2001) and Robson (2015). The following habitats were selected to examine the existing bird species.

1. Khamauktaung
2. Kyadwintaung
3. Marsh grassland (Wetland)
4. Revegetation area
5. Yamar upstream
6. Yamar downstream

Indices of species diversity and evenness

Species diversity index and evenness index values were computed following after Krabs (1999). In computation of the species diversity index value, the index of diversity (H') is an information statistic used as a diversity index.

Results and discussion

Land-cover types

The land-cover types and features of the copper mine project area were studied using GIS and RS. In land-cover type classification using ArcGIS software 10.5, land-cover types were identified in and around the copper mine project area. The land-cover types were identified as creek, tailing pond, waste dump, mine pit area, secondary forest, human habitation, revegetation, shrub land, marsh grassland (wet land), leach pad and agriculture land (Fig.1). Yamar creek is running by the project site at northern part. Tailing ponds, bare land and leach pad were components of the copper mine project. The forest is a natural secondary forest of the hills but some parts are disturbed and degraded. Waste dump occurred due to the ore extraction in the area. In GIS analysis using elevation level, the crop-land was found around and under 300-meter contour level which was the lowest level in the area (Fig. 2).

Figure 1. Land cover types of the Copper Mine project area

Figure 2. Google image map of the Copper Mine Project area

Species occurrence of birds

A total of 66 bird species which belong to 40 genera of 38 families and 16 orders were recorded at the copper mine project area during the study period from Jun to October 2019 (Table 1, 2) (Figure 3). Thirty species were found under order Passeriformes, eight species under order Charadriiformes, five species under order Pelecaniformes, three species under each order of Accipitriformes and Columbiformes, two species under each order of Anseriformes, Coraciiformes, Cuculiformes, Galliformes, Gruiformes and Suliformes, one species in each order of Apodiformes, Bucerotiformes, Caprimulgiformes, Falconiformes, and Podicipediformes.

Of these recorded species, 18 bird species which belong to nine families under six orders were aquatic birds and 48 species under 31 families of seven orders were terrestrial birds. In the recorded aquatic birds, Charadriiformes was the largest order with six species of four families. In terrestrial birds, Passeriformes was the largest order comprising 30 species of 17 families.

Among the recorded species, the species Burmese Collared-dove *Streptopelia xanthocyclus*, Hooded treepie *Crypsirina cucullata*, Burmese bush lark *Mirafra microptera*, Ayarwaddy bulbul *Pycnonotus blanfordi*, White throated babbler *Turdoides gularis*, Burmese prinia *Prinia cooki* were listed as endemic species in Myanmar and protected by the wildlife law (1994) in Myanmar.

The species River Lapwing *Vanellus duvaucelii* and Oriental darter *Anhinga melanogaster* were observed as near threaten species among the recorded species. Little Ringed Plover *Charadrius hiaticulatus*, Black-winged stilt *Himantopus himantopus*, Grey-headed lapwing *Vanellus cinereus*, Common sandpiper *Actitis hypoleucos*, Common kingfisher *Alcedo atthis*, Common Hoopoe *Upupa epops*, Black drongo *Dicrurus macrocercus*, and White wagtail *Motacilla alba* were winter visitors. Little grebe *Tachybaptus ruficollis*, Little

Egret *Egretta garzetta*, Great egret *Ardea alba*, Common moorhen *Gallinula chloropus*, and White throated kingfisher *Halcyon smyrnensis* had local movement habit. The species Spotted Dove *Streptopelia chinensis*, Little green- bee eater *Merops orientalis*, Red vented bulbul *Pycnonotus cafer*, Ayarwaddy bulbul *Pycnonotus blanfordi* were bird species which can adapt all habitat conditions, since the species were found in all habitat types in the project area.

Bird species of different habitats and index values

Khamauktaung

Twenty-six species were recorded in Khamauktaung hilly forest. Red Junglefowl *Gallus gallus*, Spotted Dove *Streptopelia chinensis*, Rock dove *Columba livia*, Plain-backed sparrow *Passer flaveolus*, Scaly-breasted Munia *Lonchura punctulata*, Red vented bulbul *Pycnonotus cafer*, Grey-breasted prinia *Prinia hodgsonii* were very common species in this area. Shannon species diversity H' index value was 1.308 and evenness J' index value was 0.924 (Table 1, Fig 3).

Kyadwintaung

Eleven bird species were recorded in Kyadwintaung regrowth forest area. Red jungle fowl *Gallus gallus*, Red vented bulbul *Pycnonotus cafer*, White throated babbler *Turdoides gularis*, Pied bush chat *Saxicola caprata* were found as very common species in the area. Shannon species diversity H' index value was 0.943 and evenness J' index value was 0.906 (Table 1, Fig 3).

Yamar Upstream

Birds were observed along the Yamar Upstream. Thirty nine bird species were recorded. Some water bird species, Little Cormorant *Microcarbo niger*, Grey heron *Ardea cinerea*, Little Egret *Egretta garzetta*, Cattle Egret *Bubulcus ibis*, Little Ringed Plover *Charadrius placidus*, River Lapwing *Vanellus duvaucelii*, Red-wattled lapwing *Vanellus indicus*, Grey-headed lapwing *Vanellus cinereus*, Common sandpiper *Actitis hypoleucos* were recorded. Among the recorded aquatic bird species, Cattle Egret was very common species and in terrestrial bird species, House crow, Pied Bushchat and Rock dove were very common species. Shannon species diversity H' index value was 1.478 and evenness J' index value was 0.929 ((Table 1, Fig 3)).

Yamar Downstream

Thirty two bird species were recorded at Yamar Down stream. Dominant water bird species within this area were Indian pond heron *Ardeola grayii*, Little Ringed Plover *Charadrius placidus* and Red-wattled lapwing *Vanellus indicus*. Very common terrestrial bird species were Rock dove *Columba livia*, Spotted-necked Dove *Streptopelia chinensis*, Scaly-breasted Munia *Lonchura punctulata*, White wagtail *Motacilla alba*. Shannon species diversity H' index value was 1.355 and evenness J' index value was 0.9 ((Table 1, Fig 3)).

Marsh Grassland (wetland)

Most part of the marsh grassland was exposed during the study period. The very common species were Chinese spot-billed duck *Anas zonorhyncha*, Lesser whistling duck *Dendrocygna javanica*, Little grebe *Tachybaptus ruficollis*, Little Cormorant *Phalacrocorax niger*. Individual number of the Chinese spot-billed duck was estimated to be 120 ducks in each flock. Shannon species diversity H' index value was 0.589 and evenness J' index value was 0.489 ((Table 1, Fig 3)).

Revegetation area

Ten bird species were recorded in the revegetation area. Spotted Dove *Streptopelia chinensis*, Little green- bee eater *Merops orientalis*, Pied bush chat *Saxicola caprata*, Ayarwaddy bulbul *Pycnonotus blanfordi*, Red vented bulbul *Pycnonotus cafer* were found as very common species in the revegetation area. Shannon species diversity H' index value was 0.868 and evenness J' index value was 0.868 ((Table 1, Fig 3)).

According to the results of the present study, Yamar upstream habitat may have good habitat quality because species number and species diversity index values are highest among the studied habitats. According to the similarity index values, Kyadwintaung and Khamauktaung have most habitat similarity when compared based on the occurrence of bird species and population size. The species diversity index values of the two habitats were high showing as conservation important habitats for the copper mine project area. Yamar stream was found as conservation important habitat of aquatic ecosystem having relatively high species number and species diversity value.

Table 1. Species diversity index value (Shannon H') and equitability (Evenness) index (Shannon J') value of the studied habitats

Habitat	Diversity index	evenness index
Khamauktaung	1.308	0.924
Kyadwintaung	0.943	0.906
Wetland	0.589	0.489
Revegetation area	0.868	0.868
Yamar upstream	1.478	0.929
Yamar downstream	1.355	0.9

Figure 3. Species diversity (Shannon H') values of different habitat types

Figure 4. Results of cluster analysis showing the distances between the studied habitats based on the bird species occurrence and population size

Table 2. Correlation matrix between the habitats

	Khamauk taung	Kyadwin taung	Wetland	Revegetation	Yamar upstream	Yamar downstrea
Khamauktaung	1.	*	*	*	*	*
Kyadwintaung	0.4821	1.	*	*	*	*
Wetland	-0.105	-0.0515	1.	*	*	*
Revegetation	0.4555	0.6463	-0.0373	1.	*	*
Yamar upstream	0.012	0.1926	-0.1197	0.276	1.	*
Yamar downstream	0.274	0.1275	-0.0969	0.2619	0.4274	1.

Conclusion

According to the nature of the copper mine, there may be some impacts on the environment and biodiversity. Secondary forest and revegetation areas observed in land-cover analysis may be important habitats for the animal species. The possible negative impacts on the Yamar stream and mrash-grassland (wetland) should be mitigated to protect the aquatic ecosystem. The vegetation and fauna of the Kyadwintaung and Khamauktaung should be conserved since the area may play an important role in the ecological web of the area. A total of 66 bird species of 38 families were recorded at the copper mine project area, where number of terrestrial bird species is higher than that of aquatic bird species. Diversity and number of birds may be used as bio-indicators in environmental monitoring of the copper mine project.

Acknowledgements

I would like to express my profound gratitude to Professor Dr. Khin Swe Wynn, Head of Zoology Department of Bago University and Professor Dr. Kyi Kyi San, Zoology Department of Bago University for their encouragement given in conducting the present research. I would like to express a deep appreciation to Dr. Win Maung, Pro-Rector (Retd), Sittway University for his suggestions and comments.

References

- Bibby, C.J, Neil. D, Burgess and David A. Hill. (1992). Bird Census Techniques. London, Academic Press.
- Bibby, C, M. Jones and S. Marsden. (1998). Expedition Field Techniques Bird Surveys. London: Kensington Gore.
- Krebs, C.J. (1999). Ecological methodology an imprint of Addison Wesley logman Inc. Newyork.
- Muir,B.G. (1998). Monywa Copper Project. Supplementary Information. Myanmar Ivanhoe Copper Company Ltd.
- Robson, C. (2015). Birds of South-East Asia: Thailand, Peninsular, Malaysia, Singapore, Vietnam, Cambodia, Laos, Myanmar
- Smythies, B.E. (2001). The Birds of Burma. Fourth Edition. Natural History Publication (Borneo), Kota Kinabalu, Malaysia.